

ISW

In Silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of In Silico Trials
Grant Agreement No. 101016503

D5.9 - ISW online Community of Practice and GSP consensus

Deliverable information	
WP number and title	WP5 - Dissemination, Communication, and RRI
Lead beneficiary	UNIBO, VPHi
Dissemination level	PU
Due date	31/12/2024
Actual date of delivery	18/12/2024
Author	Marco Viceconti
Contributors	Goran Stanic

The following document reflects only the author's view. The Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

NOTE: THIS DOCUMENT HASN'T BEEN FORMALLY APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION YET AND, THEREFORE, IT MAY BE SUBJECT TO CHANGES

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016503

Quality assurance

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implied an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by the lead beneficiary (UNIBO). All partners contributed to and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the semi-final version was submitted to internal reviewers for a final review and validation.

Version	Date	Status	Author	
V1	18-11-2024	First Draft	Marco Viceconti	
V2	21-11-2024	Second Draft	Goran Stanic	
V3	18-12-2024	Final Version	Goran Stanic	

Table of contents

1. Introduction..... 3

2. In Silico World Community of Practice 3

3. Main Achievements and Results 4

4. Good Simulation Practice consensus 4

5. Sustainability 5

1. Introduction

D5.9 is a deliverable of type DEC (Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.) where we report about the In Silico World Community of Practice online and about the consensus processes, we drove using that community platform, in particular that related to the Good Simulation Practice book.

2. In Silico World Community of Practice

The In Silico World Community of Practice (ISW_CoP) was established well before the ISW project started officially (Jan 1st, 2021); the first post on the #general channel was done on June 18th, 2019. It started as a grassroots initiative, motivated by providing a project-independent forum where all practitioners involved at any level in *in silico* medicine could find a place to discuss best practices. We chose Slack as a platform because, at that time, it was one of the few that provided the features we required, and for the type of use we had in mind, it was free.

On October 8th, 2019 I posted this message: “Dear members of the In Silico World Community of Practice, after an alpha phase that involved only a few of you, now we entered in full the beta phase of our staged release. At this point we have invited to express interest to be invited to join to all the companies member of the Board of the Avicenna Alliance. We also sent a generic description of the ISW to a couple of Program Officers in the EC who manage in silico medicine projects, who quickly forwarded it to all the coordinators of their projects portfolio. A number of membership applications are trickling in, and Roberta is processing them. When this will slow down, we will release the last piece of the puzzle, the User Manual v1.0, which sets the rules of the rules of this community. As they enter in force, you will be invited to review and comment them, and when we feel we have a solid revision (v1.1) we will end the beta phase and start contacting every research group and every company we believe should be represented in ISW. So the message is, we are quiet but we are not sleeping :-). Useless to say, any suggestion you may have to improve the community is more than welcome”. Among the EU-funded projects that supported ISW_CoP in this initial phase were Strituvad¹, CompBiomed2², and Mobilise-D³.

Thus, in some sense, the Community of Practice named the project, not vice versa. When the call (H2020-SC1-DTH-2018-2020) was published on November 19th, 2019, it came naturally to title the proposal “In Silico World”. Like ISW_CoP, the ISW project aimed to serve the entire community by lowering the barriers to the adoption of In Silico Trials.

Since its inception, the membership of ISW_CoP has grown almost linearly over its five years of existence. To date (18-11-2024), the community has 750 members with professional or educational interests in *in silico* medicine. Most participants were listening, but 217 posted at least one message, and some power users posted over 2000 messages in the five years.

Several private channels were created to provide funded projects with secure spaces where they could conduct their discussion with the members of their consortia. Public channels were created to host consensus processes that potentially interested the whole community. Among them, #in_silico_solutions allows for-profit and not-for-profit organisations to advertise their new *in silico* solutions;

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/777123/reporting>

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/823712>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/820820>

#edith_public_discussion has been the consensus forum for the EDITH roadmap⁴ and related activities; #credibility_machine_learning, hosted the discussion that produced the consensus statement on the credibility of machine learning predictors⁵; #insilicotrials_swot hosted the development of the SWOT analysis document⁶. Besides #news and #general, created at the outset, the oldest public channel is #goodsimulation practice, created on Sept 18th, 2020, in which 634 messages were exchanged to date.

Here is a recap of the most important channels:

- **Good Simulation Practices**, which led to the publication of the GSP book.
- **Credibility in Machine Learning**, to discuss with the community the details of credibility assessment for data-driven predictors.
- **EDITH Public discussion**, used to facilitate the discussion around EDITH's Roadmap toward an integrated Virtual Human Twin.
- **In Silico Solutions**, dedicated to discussions in bridging the gap from basic research where advanced models for physiology and pathophysiology are developed and bringing those models to sufficient high TRL so that they can be formally accredited by bodies such as EMA or FDA. The core of this channel is formed by 11 applications embedded in the In Silico World project that increased their TRL during the project.
- **In Silico Trials SWOT**, aimed to provide the whole community with robust and factual arguments to advocate for investing in In Silico Trials with senior management across the whole sector.

3. Main Achievements and Results

The Community had a pivotal role in achieving significant outcomes, such as:

1. Publication of "Towards Good Simulation Practice": the consensus discussion hosted by ISW_CoP drove the collaborative compilation of this book, freely available to the public in digital form, outlines essential GSP guidelines and offers invaluable insights for those involved in developing and implementing in silico trials.
2. In Silico Trials SWOT Analysis: Another significant output from the community, this analysis examines the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of adopting in silico trials, offering a strategic tool for the broader medical community.
3. Joining Global Standards Committees: Through the leadership of the ISW community, the Avicenna Alliance now participates in the IEC TC 62 & ISO/TC 276/WG5 Committees. This involvement seeks to create an IEC-ISO standard equivalent to the ASME VV-40, which could become harmonised standards in Europe, aligning in silico trials with international regulatory frameworks.

4. Good Simulation Practice consensus

"Toward Good Simulation Practice: Best Practices for the Use of Computational Modelling and Simulation in the Regulatory Process of Biomedical Products" was published by Nature Springer as an Open Access Book⁷ on February 22nd, 2024. The book has, to date, more than 34,000 views; it has been covered in 43 news articles and has already been cited in two papers, and a book has been published since then. A Google search returns

⁴ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1DWP2WtYpsMsWt8oKlhvWcXUuCWfV6Rmt>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14132097>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14011927>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-48284-7>

37,500 web pages mentioning the book or related content. All practitioners agree that it will greatly impact on In Silico Trials.

Reaching the consensus and writing the book was a massive effort; 167 experts participated in the channel and exchanged 634 messages. We produced 11 drafts of the book, which is nine chapters and nearly 50,000 words long in its final version.

5. Sustainability

The VPH Institute will ensure the long-term sustainability of the ISW_CoP platform. They are currently discussing with some other projects the opportunity to continue with Slack or whether to migrate to another platform, such as Element. But even in this case, it would be easy to migrate most of the community with little loss. In perfect Brexit spirit, ISW_CoP has been copied by InSilicoUK⁸. While the network operating the Slack community is entirely UK-based, the narrative is of an international leadership. To quote Nelson DeMille, “Plagiarism is the sincerest form of flattery”.

The Avicenna Alliance is pursuing the sustainability of the GSP work. Through their Good Simulation Practice Task Force, they explore how the concepts exposed there can become part of some future international standards or guidelines. The event⁹ organised in Sept 2023 by the Reagan-Udall Foundation for the FDA, is a perfect example of this type of work.

In conclusion, the ISW Community has played a transformative role in advancing in silico medicine by fostering international collaboration and establishing critical guidelines like GSP. Through ongoing initiatives and strategic partnerships, it continues to be at the forefront of innovation in medical research.

⁸ <https://www.insilicouk.org/>

⁹ https://reaganudall.org/sites/default/files/2024-02/GSP%20Cluster%20Summary%20Report_final%202.2.24%20for%20web.pdf